

Building an Emotionally Adaptive Conversational Agent in Spanish with Transformer-Based Emotion Classification

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Abstract. This work presents the development of an adaptive emotional conversational agent designed specifically for the Spanish language, leveraging Transformer-based language models to detect human emotions from written text. The proposed system integrates three key components: an emotion classification module trained on Spanish datasets, a rule-based empathetic response generator, and a graphical visualization tool providing real-time feedback on the user’s emotional state.

Experimental results demonstrate a global accuracy of around 79%, with strong performance in recognizing emotions such as fear and surprise, while highlighting challenges in detecting subtler emotions like joy and in distinguishing semantically similar classes such as sadness and anger. The system’s cultural and linguistic adaptation to Spanish, combined with interactive commands and emotional visualizations, enhances user experience and promotes emotional self-awareness. Limitations include the reliance on textual input without prosodic or contextual cues and the constrained variability of rule-based responses.

Keywords: Conversational agents · Emotion recognition · BERT · Affective computing.

1 Introduction

Conversational agents have grown exponentially due to advances in artificial intelligence (AI), natural language processing (NLP), and computational modeling of human behavior. These agents must not only understand user input semantically but also interpret and respond appropriately to emotions—essential in domains like education, mental health, and customer service. Integrating affective models enhances interaction quality and strengthens the user-agent alliance, increasing both the psychological and functional impact of such technologies [1].

Designing emotionally adaptive agents remains challenging. Dialogue models often produce static and impersonal responses that ignore emotional context, limiting their usefulness in empathy-driven interactions [2]. Models like BERT [3] have demonstrated strong performance in emotion classification due to their bidirectional architecture and deep contextual understanding. However, most existing systems are trained in English and lack cultural adaptation mechanisms [4].

This research addresses these gaps by developing a conversational agent in Spanish based on BERT, capable of generating empathetic, emotion-aligned responses. The goal is to provide an adaptable framework for human-machine interaction in emotionally sensitive contexts.

2 Theoretical Framework and State of the Art

Emotion detection in text requires identifying not just sentiment polarity but discrete emotions such as joy, sadness, anger, fear, or surprise. Deep learning models, particularly Transformer-based architectures, have become essential for these tasks [3]. Among them, BERT has achieved state-of-the-art results thanks to its bidirectional attention and large-scale pretraining. For Spanish applications, multilingual variants like `bert-base-multilingual-cased` are typically fine-tuned with local datasets.

Cambria et al. [6] proposed the emotion wheel, representing affective states across four dimensions: attention, sensitivity, aptitude, and valence. Zhou et al. [4] introduced the Emotional Chatting Machine (ECM), a generative model capable of producing affective responses, improving emotion accuracy by 13.2% over baseline models. However, it lacks adaptation to non-English contexts.

Hazarika et al. [7] showed that BERT-based models outperform LSTMs and CNNs for conversational emotion recognition, reaching an average F1 of 0.78 on EmotionLines. Despite this, most systems rely on English corpora, limiting cultural transferability. Existing frameworks such as Rasa or Botpress [5] offer robust dialogue logic but no built-in emotional intelligence.

Our proposal bridges these gaps by combining a Spanish emotion classifier, rule-based empathy generation, and visual affect tracking—an approach not yet reported in prior literature.

3 Methodology

The methodology comprises five main stages: (1) Dataset Construction, (2) Model Training, (3) Real-Time Inference System, (4) Affective Response Generation, and (5) Console-Based Interaction and Emotional Logging.

Fig. 1: Proposed methodology for the emotionally adaptive conversational agent.

3.1 Dataset Construction

Multiple Spanish datasets were integrated, including manually curated corpora and public resources such as TweetEval [8], translated using the Helsinki-NLP model. The data were cleaned, standardized, and balanced across emotion classes. The disgust category was excluded due to low representation and semantic ambiguity.

3.2 Model Training

The base model `BertForSequenceClassification` was fine-tuned with five epochs, AdamW optimizer, and a learning rate of 2×10^{-5} . Evaluation used accuracy and weighted F1-score. Stratified sampling preserved label distribution. Tokenization employed `bert-base-multilingual-cased` with maximum length 128. Results were evaluated using precision, recall, and F1 metrics, and analyzed via confusion matrix.

3.3 Real-Time Inference System

The inference module applies the trained model to new text inputs, returning predicted emotion and confidence. Implemented within an `EmotionDetector` class, it ensures compatibility with both CPU and GPU environments. Softmax normalization converts logits to probabilities, and logging mechanisms capture low-confidence predictions.

3.4 Affective Response Generation

A rule-based response generator maps detected emotions to empathetic message templates. Random selection introduces variability, maintaining tone and emotional coherence. Though simple, this approach ensures conversational stability and content safety.

3.5 Console Interaction and Emotional Logging

The system operates via a CLI interface. Users input free text after initiating the session. Each message is classified, and responses are generated accordingly. Logs track emotional frequencies and provide visual feedback via bar charts (Fig. 2) and emotional timelines (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2: Emotion bar chart representing the user's state during a session.

Fig. 3: Timeline of dominant emotions across sessions.

4 Results

This section presents the evaluation results of the trained emotion classifier and its conversational deployment. Metrics include per-class precision, recall, and F1-score.

4.1 Emotion Detection Results

Table 1: Evaluation Metric Results (averaged per emotion class)

Emotion	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Anger	0.82	0.76	0.79	78
Fear	0.87	0.84	0.86	77
Joy	0.71	0.71	0.71	78
Sadness	0.73	0.82	0.77	78
Surprise	0.83	0.82	0.82	77
AVG	0.79	0.79	0.79	78

Fear and surprise achieved the best F1-scores (0.86 and 0.82), while joy showed lower accuracy. Misclassifications mainly occurred between sadness and anger, reflecting emotional overlap in natural language. The overall macro F1-score (0.79) indicates robust model reliability for Spanish emotional text.

Fig. 4: Confusion matrix of the trained model.

4.2 Real-Time Interaction Results

The conversational agent displayed stable, coherent responses. Long messages yielded more accurate predictions than short or ambiguous inputs. For example, the model correctly classified an extended complaint as anger (confidence 0.97) but misclassified “me siento furioso” as fear (0.49). This reflects limited generalization to minimal-context inputs.

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> Me molesta profundamente que las personas no valoren el esfuerzo que uno hace, y lo peor es
que te critican sin conocer tu situación
2025-07-07 09:49:01,117 - INFO - Texto: 'Me molesta profundamente que las personas no valoren
el esfuerzo que uno hace, y lo peor es que te critican sin conocer tu situación' -> Emoción:
nger (Score: 0.8196)

🗨️ Emoción detectada: Anger (Confianza: 0.82)
🗨️ Está bien sentirse así. A veces, expresar el enojo es el primer paso para superarlo.
> Me siento furioso
2025-07-07 09:49:26,103 - INFO - Texto: 'Me siento furioso' -> Emoción: fear (Score: 0.5046)

🗨️ Emoción detectada: Fear (Confianza: 0.50)
🗨️ Entiendo que eso pueda dar miedo. Es una reacción natural.

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Fig. 5: Example of real-time interaction with the conversational agent.

4.3 Discussion

An average F1-score of 0.79 indicates competitive performance compared with related English-based studies (0.75–0.83). The confusion between sadness and anger aligns with known semantic overlap in emotional language. These results confirm the feasibility of applying BERT-based emotion models to Spanish dialogue while highlighting challenges of brevity and ambiguity.

From an application perspective, this accuracy supports deployment in educational, psychological, and service contexts where reliable emotional understanding enhances user engagement and empathy.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

5.1 Contributions

This study presented a Spanish emotionally adaptive conversational agent integrating BERT-based emotion detection, empathetic rule-based responses, and affective visualization. With 79% overall accuracy, it demonstrates strong detection of fear and surprise and contributes a linguistically adapted framework for affective computing in Spanish.

5.2 Limitations

Some confusion persists between semantically related emotions such as sadness and anger. The system also depends solely on textual cues and uses static rule-based responses, limiting conversational diversity in extended interactions.

5.3 Future Work

Future research will focus on adding affective memory to retain emotional context, integrating generative models (e.g., GPT-based architectures) for more natural empathetic dialogue, and validating the system in real-world educational and psychological applications.

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